

Seaweed: a prominent source of protein and other nutrients

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Abstract

It is crucially important to provide a sufficient food supply to ensure food security in the context of an increasing global population, shrinking cropland, and changes in the environment. The availability of adequate nourishment is important for both human and animal health. A strong dietary protein source is animal products, particularly their proteins, however, because of the large carbon footprint associated with their production, efforts to find alternative protein sources have been made. This study sought to provide more information on the development of scientific research into the nutritional properties of seaweed as an alternative source of nutrients. When it comes to mariculture or controlled fisheries, seaweed has a clean, renewable supply that is natural, sustainable, and has a natural origin. Being a good source of protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and minerals, seaweed has a high nutritional value, derived from seawater based on environmental and seasonal factors. To increase seaweed production to a commercial level and win over consumers all over the world, efforts must be made to sustainable seaweed cultivation and better management. Furthermore, more study is required to optimize the process of seaweed protein extraction for applications in food and nutraceuticals.

Introduction

Humans generally rely on livestock and seeds of terrestrial plants for sources of high-quality protein. But the increased use of

farmland and freshwater contributes to climate change and jeopardizes the viability of the world's food supply chain (Springmann et al., 2018). Food systems were responsible for 35 percent of all manmade greenhouse

gas (GHG) production, with animal-based diets having a greater than 50 percent impact (Xu et al., 2021). As a result, one of the most viable methods to achieve global sustainability is to look for alternative sources of protein, and seaweed can be a notable substitute for livestock and terrestrial plants. This is because of the anticipated global food scarcity as well as other economic and environmental concerns.

Seaweeds are Thallophytes because they are autotrophic, simple in structure, and have little to no cellular differentiation. Since they lack a structured vascular system for receiving nutrients, seaweeds are not considered real plants. According to the taxonomy, they may be divided into three groups: Rhodophyta, Ochrophyta (or, Phaeophyta), and Chlorophyta, which correspond to red, brown, and green algae, respectively (Beetul et al., 2016; Ibáñez and Herrero, 2017; Ullah et al., 2023). Red algae, also known as Rhodophyta, are the most primitive group of algae, making up roughly 6000 species, and they may be found in a variety of environments (Lozano and Díaz, 2020). A vast family of marine algae known as brown algae or Ochrophyta (Phaeophyta), has over 1750 species (Lozano and Díaz, 2020). Its name comes from the coloring, which ranges from yellow to dark brown. Green algae or Chlorophyta are less prevalent, with 1836 species in around 285 genera (Wehr, 2015). Its coloration ranges from greenish yellow to dark green.

Seaweed is a significant nutrient source with potential uses in food and medicine (Rameshkumar et al., 2012). According to Rajapakse and Kim (2011), Asian countries like China, Japan, and Korea have consumed a lot of these marine algae during the past few decades; over 66% of the species are regularly utilized as ingredients in their cuisine. Seaweed is now consumed by numerous nations, including those in Europe, the Pacific Ocean, and other regions. Several varieties of seaweed, particularly protein-rich seaweeds, are used as food in many different countries worldwide (Haque et al., 2009). A number of edible seaweeds have high levels

of proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals (Norziah and Ching, 2000). Seaweed's nutritional content varies depending on the species, region, seasonality, temperature, and rainfall (Kaehler and Kennish, 1996). Being a source of sustenance for both humans and animals, seaweed plays a significant role in both nature and human existence. As fresh or dried veggies, salads, or as components in a broad range of prepared dishes, they are nutritiously useful (Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997). According to various reports (Pereira, 2011; Mohibbullah et al., 2022), there are 145 distinct types of seaweeds utilized for human consumption, of which 79 are red seaweed, 38 are brown seaweeds, and 28 are green seaweeds. Recently, 33 different seaweeds- 20 brown, 10 red, and 3 green, have been identified as the primary edible seaweeds (Pereira, 2016; Mohibbullah et al., 2022). In contrast to other aquatic resources, seaweed can be quite important in a variety of ways. Seaweed should receive a lot of attention in order to partially offset the food shortage and cover the nutritional gap necessary to boost the economies of various nations. They also have been utilized in the food industry as sources of phycocolloids, thickening agents, and gelling agents (Estevam et al., 2016; Scieszka and Klewicka, 2019). Seaweed is also a superb source of chemical compounds, including a wide range of physiologically active secondary metabolites, as well as polysaccharides, minerals, and vitamins (Villarreal-Gómez et al., 2010). These bioactive substances are molecules that may be created from either natural or synthetic sources and are physiologically tested for their potential medicinal effects. There has long been a connection between the activity of these bioactive compounds and health, and it now appears that bioactive food ingredients can change the genetic expression of a variety of cellular processes, potentially affecting health status or providing beneficial antioxidant or enzyme inhibitory activities (MacArtain et al., 2007). There may be antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, and

antiviral properties in certain seaweeds (Venugoapl, 2009).

This review presents the nutritional composition of different species of seaweed around the world. We have extensively studied the information on seaweed with special reference to its nutritive value. We also consider their production volumes (FAO, 2022). The database contains more than 80 articles including research articles, reviews, case studies, Ph.D. research, annual reports, and much more current research. The findings might be compiled to give the scientific community the most recent knowledge and to encourage the appropriate

use of seaweed with respect to their nutritional value.

Global seaweed production

The technique of growing and producing seaweed has greatly expanded, and it is now essential to the fishery sector (Cai et al., 2021). Data from the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2022) show that between 1950 and 2020, the world's production of seaweed (both from farmed and wild) increased from 0.56 million tons to 36.23 million tons (Figure 1). In the past two decades, the yield of seaweed (from both farmed and natural sources) has about tripled (FAO, 2022).

Figure 1. Status of world seaweed production (million tons) from 1950 to 2020 (FAO, 2022)

Around 97% of the world's seaweed production in 2020 came from marine farming. The 5 major continents produce the majority of the seaweed consumed worldwide. Ninety-nine percent of seaweed in Asia is cultured. China, which produces 58.18% of the world's seaweed, is at the top position in terms of production. The second is Indonesia, a significant producer of seaweed that accounts for 26.72% of world production. A large number of seaweed species, including red, brown and green

seaweeds, are found in South Korea, which accounts for 4.89% of the world's total seaweed production. The Philippines holds 4.06% of the world market for seaweed culture. Japan produces 1.27% of the world's seaweed. Over 95% of the seaweed consumed in North America comes from natural resources, making up around 1.36% of the world's total seaweed production. Chile accounts for 1.19% of the world's seaweed production, making it the leading producer in America. Although brown seaweed has

recently been cultivated, the majority of brown seaweeds (Ochrophyta) and red seaweeds (Rhodophyta) come from natural riverbeds. Algae are mostly collected from natural sources in Canada, the United States, and Peru. Ninety-six percent of the seaweed consumed in Europe comes from natural sources. Cultivation has only been tested in Europe since 2010. Around 0.41% of the seaweed in the world is found in Africa. Oceania makes up around 0.05% of world seaweed production (FAO, 2022).

In 2020, over 93% of the seaweed farmed around the globe came from eight different species. *Laminaria japonica* makes up roughly 35.5% of worldwide seaweed cultivation and is mostly used in salads, sauces, and other condiments. More than 27% of the carrageenan utilized for extraction came from the algae *Kappaphycus* and *Euचेuma* (FAO, 2022). According to FAO (2022), *Gracilaria*, *Undaria*, and *Porphyra* each contributed 14.8%, 8%, and 6.3% of the total seaweed production, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Seaweed aquaculture production (%) per species in the year 2020 (FAO, 2022).

Nutritional components of seaweeds

Red seaweeds

The group of seaweeds existing with the greatest diversity, dominance, and economic value is red seaweeds. They contain phycobilin (phycoerythrin and phycocyanin), a photosynthetic pigment that gives them their color in addition to carotene and xanthophyll (Salamanca et al., 2005). They mostly grow on dark ocean bottoms and may be seen in the intertidal and subtidal zones at depths of up to 40-250 m (Pineiro, 2012). *Porphyra sp.*, *Euचेuma sp.*, *Gracilaria sp.*, and *Kappaphycus sp.* are the most common types of red seaweeds (Cotas et al., 2020).

The protein, lipid, ash, moisture, carbohydrate, and fiber content of different red seaweed species in the world is shown in Table 1. The range of red seaweeds' mean protein content is 4.07 to 36.88%. Since they contain more protein than the green and brown seaweed species, the red seaweed species are of great interest (Cerna, 2011; Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012). Lipid content ranged from 0.02 to 5.0%. Ash content ranged from 4.1 to 51.16%. Moisture content ranged from 2.4 to 89.78%. Carbohydrate content ranged from 1.8 to 63.12%. Fiber content ranged from 2.02 to 53.2%.

Table 1. Proximate composition of red seaweeds from different regions of the world.

Seaweed	Protein	Lipid	Ash	Moisture	Carbohydrate	Fibre	Location	Reference
<i>Hypnea</i> sp.	23.64	1.46	7.05	15.43	46.71	5.72	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Gracilaria verrucosa</i>	16.51	0.20	46.72	79.78			Kilinochchi and Kalpitiya, Sri Lanka	Premadasa and Edirisinghe, 2022
<i>Gracilaria corticate</i>	21.66	0.24	44.34	89.78			Kilinochchi and Kalpitiya, Sri Lanka	Premadasa and Edirisinghe, 2022
<i>Ahnfeltia plicata</i>	20.1		23.2		30.2		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Broggiartella byssoides</i>	15.8		41.9		24.0		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Ceramium</i> sp.	15.8		32.8		35.2		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Chondrus crispus</i>	10.3		27.2		52.6		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Delesseria sanguinea</i>	18.3		31.2		25.9		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Dilsea carnosa</i>	15.2		24.0		47.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Furcellaria lumbricalis</i>	17.1		32.9		29.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Rhodomela confervoides</i>	14.8		32.2		34.0		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Digenea simplex</i>	21.14	2.3			42.4	10.55	Hurghada Red Sea coast, Egypt	Alwaleed, 2019
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	5.07	0.55	28.38	18.84	44.76	2.42	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Centroceras clavulatum</i>	4.78	0.75	36.69	23.54	32.24	2.02	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Hypnea spinella</i>	8.02	1.44	33.07	18.61	34.46	4.41	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Kappaphycus alvarezii</i>	4.86	0.57	27.49	22.77	41.15	3.18	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Digenea simplex</i>	5.3	0.8	24.7	2.4	35.7	28.4	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019
<i>Porphyra</i> sp.	21.14	0.19	5.4	14.30	20.59	38.24	Sri Lanka	Jayakody et al., 2019
<i>Tricleocarpa fragilis</i>	4.07	0.84	42.29	24.05	28.76	12.05	Andaman Sea, India	Banu and Mishra, 2018
<i>Gracilaria corticate</i>	12.18	0.20	51.16		23.53	4.37	Red sea coast, Eritrea	Kasimala et al., 2017
<i>Aghardhiella subulate</i>	8.8	2.0			4.5		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Amphiroa anceps</i>	9.5	1.0			4.8		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Amphiroa fragilissima</i>	8.6	4.8			4.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Digenea simplex</i>	8.4	4.8			4.6		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Gelidium acerosa</i>	8.2	0.8			10.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Gracilaria edulis</i>	8.6	4.2			10.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Gracilaria foliifera</i>	8.6	2.2			1.8		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Gracilaria opuntia</i>	8.5	5.0			7.6		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017

<i>Hypnea valentiae</i>	9.0	3.0			3.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Kappaphycus alvarezii</i>	8.8	3.8			5.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Laurencia papillosa</i>	8.6	4.5			9.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Gracilaria changii</i>	12.57	0.30	40.30	5.32	41.52	29.44	Malaysia	Chan and Matanjun, 2017
<i>Hypnea musciformis</i>	13.73	0.34	9.76	24.31	46.26	5.6	St. Martin's Island	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Jania rubens</i>	5.7	0.41	16.27	8.58	63.14	5.9	St. Martin's Island	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Gracilaria gracilis</i>	20.2	0.60	24.8	7.99	46.6		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Osmundea pinnatifida</i>	23.8	0.9	30.62	11.77	32.4		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Grateloupia turuturu</i>	22.5	2.2	20.52	11.68	43.2		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Laurencia capsica</i>	22.22	0.30	26.82		25.50		Southern Caspian Sea	Neda et al., 2014
<i>Porphyra tenera</i>	36.88	2.25	9.07	3.66			Wando, Korea and Jiangsu, China	Hwang et al., 2013
<i>Porphyra haitanensis</i>	32.16	1.96	8.78	6.74			Wando, Korea and Jiangsu, China	Hwang et al., 2013
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	7.1	2.1	29.0		27.1		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Champia parvula</i>	10.0	4.6	38.5		34.0		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Hypnea cervicornis</i>	11.1	3.7	33.0		25.2		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Gracillaria corticate</i>	10.6	5.0	40.1		43.4		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Jania rubens</i>	9.8	1.7	44.5		29.8		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Laurencia papillosa</i>	11.7	3.5	34.0		24.6		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Hypnea pannosa</i>	16.31	1.56	18.65	12.35	22.89	40.59	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Siddique et al., 2013
<i>Hypnea musciformis</i>	18.64	1.27	21.57	11.54	20.60	21.57	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Siddique et al., 2013
<i>Gelidiella acerosa</i>	6.1	2.8	10.3	12.15	10.5	13.45	Gulf of Mannar	Syad et al., 2013
<i>Hypnea valentiae</i>	16.5	2.8	21.8	10.8	31.8		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012
<i>Gracilaria corticate</i>	19.3	1.8	23.1	9.2	43.0		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012
<i>Gelidiella acerosa</i>	31.9	1.9			16.4		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Gracilaria crassa</i>	15.0	2.0			16.9		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Hypnea musciformis</i>	14.8	1.2					Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Gracilaria folifera</i>	6.98	3.23			22.32		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Hypnea valentiae</i>	8.34	1.5			23.60		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	11.96	1.7			23.54		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Euचेuma cottonii</i>	9.76	1.10	46.19	10.55	26.49	5.91	North Borneo, Malaysia	Matanjun et al., 2009
<i>Gracilaria cervicornis</i>	19.7	0.43	7.72	14.66	63.12	5.65	Northwest of Brazil	Marinho-Soriano et al., 2006

<i>Gracilaria changgi</i>	6.90	3.30	22.70			24.7	West coast of Malaysia	Norziah and Ching, 2000
<i>Hypnea japonica</i>	19.00	1.42	22.10	9.95	4.28	53.2	Northeast of Hong Kong	Wong and Cheung, 2000
<i>Hypnea charoides</i>	18.40	1.48	22.80	10.90	7.02	50.3	Northeast of Hong Kong	Wong and Cheung, 2000
<i>Asparagopsis taxiformis</i>	10.56	0.02	4.1	61.64	23.68		St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Mehedi et al., 1999
<i>Gelidium pristoides</i>	11.80	0.90	14.00		43.10			Foster and Hodgson, 1998
<i>Gracilaria cornea</i>	5.47		29.06		36.29	5.21	Yucatan	Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997
<i>Eucheuma isiforme</i>	12.10		34.00		25.89	3.21	Yucatan	Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997

Brown seaweeds

Brown seaweeds or Ochrophyta (Phaeophyta) are multicellular, highly evolved algae that are usually exclusively found in cold coastal waters and very rarely in freshwater. *Laminaria* sp., *Sargassum* sp., *Ascophyllum* sp., and *Undaria* sp. are the principal species of brown seaweed (Li et al., 2021). Fucoxanthin and other xanthophyll pigments, which conceal chlorophyll *a* and *c*, β -carotene, and other xanthophyll pigments, predominate in brown seaweeds, giving them their color. Alginic acid and cellulose make up their cells. Brown seaweeds are often found along coastal cold-water bodies and have stores of polysaccharides and alcohol. Brown seaweeds have an extremely flexible body that enables them to bend or orient in response to wave motion. These are the biggest seaweeds and may grow to a length of 35 meters (Pineiro, 2012).

The nutrient content of different brown seaweed species in the world is shown in Table 2. The average protein content of red seaweeds ranges from 3.78 to 17.80%. Lipid content ranges from 0.15 to 8.0%. Ash content ranges from 4.08 to 76.42%. Moisture content ranges from 8.71 to 80.25%. Carbohydrate content ranges from 1.5 to 90.01%. Fiber content ranges from 0.83 to 51.77%.

Table 2. Proximate composition of brown seaweeds from different regions of the world.

Seaweed	Protein	Lipid	Ash	Moisture	Carbohydrate	Fibre	Location	Reference
<i>Nizamuddinina zanardinii</i>	3.86	0.24	16.34	8.71	65.05	5.23	Southern Oman	Al-Souti et al., 2022
<i>Sargassum</i> sp.	13.36	0.39	19.44	20.29	38.75	7.78	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Hydroclathrus clathratus</i>	7.20	0.15	61.98	17.79	10.70	2.19	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Padina pavonica</i>	7.64	0.23	54.51	12.09	24.72	0.83	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Colpomenia sinuosa</i>	7.15	0.20	57.21	12.74	17.04	5.68	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Petalonia fascia</i>	7.24	2.75	18.51	17.80	43.63	10.08	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Dictyota ciliolata</i>	7.69	1.68	44.49	29.65	14.74	1.76	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Turbinaria ornata</i>	16.79	0.37	26.11	76.33			Kilinochchi and Kalpitiya, Sri Lanka	Premadasa and Edirisinghe, 2022
<i>Sargassum polycystum</i>	17.80	1.94	29.45	80.25			Kilinochchi and Kalpitiya, Sri Lanka	Premadasa and Edirisinghe, 2022
<i>Sargassum wightii</i>	6.43	3.09	19.87	21.33	45.66	24.93	Indian Coast	Kumar et al., 2021
<i>Cystoseira compressa</i>	8.91	1.83	32.04		39.62		West Algerian coast	Oucif et al., 2020
<i>Cystoseira stricta</i>	14.14	2.71	24.61		35.45		West Algerian coast	Oucif et al., 2020
<i>Cystoseira elongata</i>	5.85	0.64	76.42		13.40		West Algerian coast	Oucif et al., 2020
<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>	5.9		20.2		31.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Chorda filum</i>	6.3		39.0		29.2		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Desmarestia aculeata</i>	11.5		25.4		30.1		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Fucus serratus</i>	7.1		20.3		28.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	7.1		24.4		26.6		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Halidrys siliquosa</i>	7.9		17.6		23.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Laminaria digitata</i>	6.6		16.8		51.9		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Saccharina latissimi</i>	6.9		11.8		55.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Sphacelaria cirrosa</i>	12.0		28.8		26.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Sargassum polycystum</i>	5.85	0.45			90.01	33.95	Hurghada Red Sea coast, Egypt	Alwaleed, 2019
<i>Cystoseria myrica</i>	10.0	2.2			48.0	38.24	Hurghada Red Sea coast, Egypt	Alwaleed, 2019
<i>Padina pavonica</i>	5.53	0.83	24.85	20.47	43.39	4.94	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Spatoglossum schroederi</i>	5.21	3.07	34.58	12.84	40.04	4.28	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Hormophysa cuneiformis</i>	4.8	0.92	27.5	10.8	23.4	27.6	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019
<i>Padina boergesenii</i>	5.9	3.8	35.8	9	24.7	36.2	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019
<i>Polycladia myrica</i>	7.1	1.3	27.8	9.7	30.4	34.7	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019

<i>Sargassum aquifolium</i>	5.4	3.1	30.8	9.1	29.3	33.1	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019
<i>Chnoospora minima</i>	13.70	0.21	17.20	13.24	3.87	51.77	Sri Lanka	Jayakody et al., 2019
<i>Sargassum linearifolium</i>	6.93	1.42	26.86		27.82	19.97	Red sea coast, Eritrea	Kasimala et al., 2017
<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>	8.70	3.62	30.89	11.08			Atlantic Ocean	Lorenzo et al., 2017
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	12.99	3.75	20.71	11.23			Atlantic Ocean	Lorenzo et al., 2017
<i>Bifurcaria bifurcata</i>	8.92	6.54	31.68	7.95			Atlantic Ocean	Lorenzo et al., 2017
<i>Cystoseira indica</i>	7.5	3.1			4.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	8.5	5.4			4.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Hydroclathrus clathratus</i>	8.2	2.1			2.5		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Padina boergesenii</i>	8.6	8.0			1.5		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Padina tetrastrumatica</i>	8.9	7.4			3.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Sargassum cinereum</i>	8.8	3.0			3.9		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Sargassum cinctum</i>	8.6	3.0			3.5		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Sargassum cristaeofolium</i>	8.0	2.3			4.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Turbinaria conoides</i>	8.8	3.2			3.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Turbinaria decurrens</i>	8.4	6.8			1.5		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Turbinaria ornata</i>	8.3	6.6			3.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Padina tetrastrumatica</i>	12.29	0.98	27.95	15.68	36.30	6.8	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Sargassum oligocystum</i>	8.19	0.83	12.94	21.09	51.75	5.2	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Sargassum muticum</i>	16.9	1.45	22.94	9.64	49.3		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	14.44	1.1	28.15	10.88	45.6		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Colpomenia sinuosa</i>	11.0	3.5	25.5		22.3		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Sargassum wightii</i>	14.82	2.72	25	22.4	9.5	17	Gulf of Mannar	Syad et al., 2013
<i>Sargassum polycystum</i>	7.78	0.71	21.87		34.93	34.71	Malaysia	Ahmad et al., 2012
<i>Padina gymnospora</i>	5.93	0.51	45.04		26.86	21.66	Malaysia	Ahmad et al., 2012
<i>Sargassum ilicifolium</i>	8.9	2.0	29.9	10.4	32.9		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012
<i>Colpomenia sinuosa</i>	9.2	1.5	28.1	11.5	32.1		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012
<i>Dictyota dichotoma</i>	9.9	1.5			16.8		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Padina pavonica</i>	13.8	1.4			15.0		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Turbinaria ornate</i>	14.0	1.7			17.2		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Padina gymnospora</i>	17.08	1.4			21.88		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008

<i>Sargassum tenerimum</i>	12.42	1.46			23.55		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Tubunaria conoides</i>	12.01	2.4			23.9		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Sargassum wightii</i>	11.7	2.33			23.50		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Colpomenia sinuosa</i>	10.7	2.33			22.46		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Sargassum vulgare</i>	13.6	0.4	19.4	14.33	61.6	7.7	Northwest of Brazil	Marinho-Soriano et al., 2006
<i>Hydroclathrus clathratus</i>	4.24	1.67	5.22	70.40	18.47		St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Mehedi et al., 1999
<i>Colpomenia sinuosa</i>	3.78	1.10	4.08	68.44	22.61		St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Mehedi et al., 1999
<i>Sargassum filipendula</i>	8.72		44.29		3.73	6.57	Yucatan	Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997
<i>Padina gymnospora</i>	9.86		36.61		1.86	9.07	Yucatan	Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997

Green seaweeds

Chlorophyll *a* and chlorophyll *b*, found in chloroplasts, are the primary components that give green seaweed their distinctive color. Similar amounts of these pigments are present in higher plants. In littoral zones, green seaweed is the most prevalent. The most prevalent green seaweed seen in various settings are sea lettuce (*Ulva* sp.) (Pineiro, 2012). Often used as food sources include green seaweeds, i.e., *Ulva* sp., *Monostroma* sp., *Caulerpa* sp., and *Codium* sp. (Kılınc et al., 2013).

Table 3 presents the composition of several green seaweed species from across the world in terms of protein, lipids, ash, moisture, carbohydrates, and fibers. The range of green seaweeds' mean protein content is 3.25 to 29.5%. Because of changes in geography and species, various species may have variable protein contents (Dhargalkar et al., 1980; Haroon et al., 2000). Seaweed has very few lipids (Burtin, 2003). Green seaweed has a lipid content that varies from 0.08 to 8.2% of dry weight. Because their anionic carboxyl, sulfate, and phosphate groups are excellent binding sites for holding metals, seaweed often has a high ash content (Davis et al., 2003). This characteristic consistently leads to the accumulation of various mineral elements in substantial quantities (Matanjun et al., 2009).

Green seaweed has an ash concentration that ranges from 9.9% to 55.11%, and a moisture content that ranges from 6.1% to 24.6% of its dry weight. The primary element in the proximate makeup of seaweeds is carbohydrates (Rohani-Ghadikolaei et al., 2012). The percentage of carbohydrates varies from 2.8% to 67.4%. Green seaweed has between 0.23% and 54.9% of its weight in fibers. Seaweed species differ in terms of developmental stages, seasonal environmental conditions, and photosynthetic capacity, and this may explain the large variation in their crude fiber content (Wong and Cheung, 2000; Siddique et al., 2013).

Table 3. Proximate composition of green seaweeds from different regions of the world.

Seaweed	Protein	Lipid	Ash	Moisture	Carbohydrate	Fibre	Location	Reference
<i>Ulva fasciata</i>	13.92	0.08	24.22	8.22	51.31	5.45	Southern Oman	Al-Souti et al., 2022
<i>Ulva</i> sp.	18.35	0.59	32.40	15.79	32.65	0.23	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Chowdhury et al., 2022
<i>Ulva rigida</i>	27.11	2.71	19.63	22.61	31.87	18.65	Indian Coast	Kumar et al., 2021
<i>Cladophora rupestris</i>	18.4		20.7		39.9		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Cladophora</i> sp.	13.9		36.5		34.8		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	9.0		31.9		36.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	9.3		32.2		34.7		Swedish west coast	Olsson et al., 2020
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	13.61	1.00	26.36		46.11		West Algerian coast	Oucif et al., 2020
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	12.54	0.98	27.13		42.81		West Algerian coast	Oucif et al., 2020
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	16.5	4.0			49.0	5.93	Hurghada Red Sea coast, Egypt	Alwaleed, 2019
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	5.54	0.33	26.99	20.67	45.52	0.96	Salinas Bay, Ecuador	D'Armas et al., 2019
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	4.8	5.2	31.5	6.1	35.5	31.9	Red Sea coast, Egypt	El-Manawy et al., 2019
<i>Ulva fasciata</i>	11.84	0.28	18.05	18.11	7.68	44.04	Sri Lanka	Jayakody et al., 2019
<i>Ulva clathrata</i>	13.64	0.80	39.42		28.97	17.17	Red sea coast, Eritrea	Kasimala et al., 2017
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	8.8	8.0			3.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i> var. <i>macrophysa</i>	8.8	0.4			4.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Caulerpa scalpelliformis</i>	8.6	3.6			6.4		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Chaetomorpha antennina</i>	9.0	8.0			4.6		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Chlorodesmis hildebrandtii</i>	8.7	2.5			3.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Cladophora vagabunda</i>	9.0	2.0			4.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Halimeda gracilis</i>	9.0	4.2			3.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Ulva fasciata</i>	8.8	3.0			3.0		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	8.6	3.0			2.8		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Valoniopsis pachynema</i>	8.9	8.2			3.2		Southeast Coast of India	Roy and Anantharaman, 2017
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	22.25	2.65	9.9	16.36	44.04	4.8	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	19.5	0.3	15.2	24.6	35.5	4.9	St. Martin's Island, Bangladesh	Khan et al., 2016
<i>Codium tomentosum</i>	18.8	3.6	35.9	9.0	32.8		West Coast of Portugal	Rodrigues et al., 2015
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	20.82	0.20	17.87		24.00		Southern Caspian Sea	Neda et al., 2014

<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	28.08	1.62	25.08		21.70		Southern Caspian Sea	Neda et al., 2014
<i>Caulerpa sertulariodes</i>	11.9	2.7	42.5		23.5		Northern Persian Gulf	Mohammadi et al., 2013
<i>Caulerpa lentillifera</i>	13.24	0.17	14.10		53.08	19.40	Malaysia	Ahmad et al., 2012
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	10.52	0.15	10.64		67.40	11.29	Malaysia	Ahmad et al., 2012
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	17.1	3.6	12.4	6.8	59.1		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaie et al., 2012
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	10.5	2.9	22.4	10.6	35.5		Persian Gulf of Iran	Rohani-Ghadikolaie et al., 2012
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	8.46	7.87	19.59	14.95		54.90	Tunisia	Yaich et al., 2011
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	13.1	0.85			16.9		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Ulva reticulata</i>	14.0	1.5			15.1		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	20.8	1.2			14.8		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Halimeda macroloba</i>	29.5	0.3			17.1		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Halimeda tuna</i>	23.0	3.5			17.0		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2009
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	16.38	1.33			23.84		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	3.25	1.6			23.6		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Codium tomentosum</i>	6.13	2.53			20.47		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Ulva clathrata</i>	11.1	4.6			23.55		Southeast Coast of India	Manivannan et al., 2008
<i>Caulerpa racemosa</i>	3.98		55.11		3.60	1.36	Yucatan	Robledo and Freile-Pelegrin, 1997

Other nutritional components of seaweeds

Seaweed, which is renowned for its high amount of minerals (between 8 and 40% of the dry weight), obtains a large amount of minerals from the marine environment. These include micronutrients like iron, iodine, zinc, copper, molybdenum, selenium, fluoride, manganese, boron, nickel, cobalt, etc. as well as important minerals like sodium, calcium, magnesium, potassium, phosphorus, chloride, and sulfate (Lorenzo et al., 2017; Peñalver et al., 2020). The method of processing and mineralization methods used (Rupérez et al., 2002) as well as the taxonomic group, regional, seasonal, and physiological variables may all affect the mineral composition (Mabeau and Fleurence, 1993). Consuming seaweed enables individuals to meet their daily dietary iodine requirements, as seaweed serves as a substantial source of this essential element (Rajapakse and Kim, 2011). Seaweed can be used as a dietary supplement to assist in meeting the daily requirements for several macro minerals and trace elements due to their high mineral content.

According to Matanjun et al. (2009), seaweed contains almost all amino acids. A large number of seaweed species are regarded as excellent sources of protein since they contain a lot of essential amino acids (EAAs). Several seaweed species with high valine, phenylalanine, and threonine content have comparable EAA patterns in their proteins. Of all EAAs, methionine and cysteine levels in seaweed are due to their sulfur content (Artemisia et al., 2019). Seaweed may be a rich functional component since sulfur-containing amino acids are essential for human protein synthesis and development. The total of these amino acids was much greater than many terrestrial plants. Seaweed amino acids (such as glutamic and aspartic acids) may make up to 30% of the non-EAAs' total amino acid content, greatly enhancing the

distinct umami flavor of seaweed (Harrysson et al., 2018).

Due to their abundance in essential fatty acids, seaweed may be more effective as a nutritional supplement or as a component of a healthy diet (Admassu et al., 2015). Several seaweed species' fatty acids exhibit anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties and their fatty acid content changes according to the season (Belattmania et al., 2016).

Vitamins are crucial nutrients for carrying out certain necessary bodily tasks as well as for ensuring wellness (Bellows et al., 2012). All vitamins, both essential and non-essential, are abundant in seaweeds (Ganesan et al., 2019). Certain seaweeds include vitamins with several health benefits and antioxidant activity, which helps to lower a number of health issues like high blood pressure, cardiovascular disease, and cancer risk (Gupta et al., 2020). Diverse seaweeds have been shown to include the water-soluble vitamins B1, B2, B12, and vitamin C, as well as the fat-soluble vitamins, such as vitamin E and β -carotene which is the precursor of vitamin A (Škrovánková, 2011).

Natural pigments are fat-soluble polyenes that have a variety of biological roles in addition to serving as colorants (Li and Kim, 2011). Seaweeds, plants, mammals, and invertebrates all have pigments in varying amounts. A possible source of distinctive natural pigments is seaweed (Pangestuti and Kim, 2015). The three kinds of pigments found in seaweeds are carotenoids, phycobiliproteins, and chlorophylls (Pereira et al., 2014). Since chlorophyll cannot be absorbed by the human body, it is converted into the easily absorbed compounds pyropheophytin, pheophorbide, and pheophytin in processed vegetable meals. Chlorophylls have an antimutagenic action and may be essential in preventing cancer (Ferruzzi and Blakeslee, 2007). Red seaweed contains large amounts of water-soluble pigments called phycobiliproteins

(Mihova et al., 1996). Phycobilins have neuroprotective, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects (Holdt and Kraan, 2011). The xanthophylls (zeaxanthin, violaxanthin, lutein, fucoxanthin, neoxanthin, antheraxanthin, and astaxanthin) and carotenes are carotenoids found in seaweeds (Manivasagan et al., 2018). Pigment-rich seaweed might be utilized as nutritional supplements.

5. Conclusion

A growing alternative source of nutrients is seaweed. Seaweed has the potential as a source of dietary supplements for both human and animal nutrition as well as a sustainable functional food. They could potentially provide a solution to the global human nutritional crisis. If ingested consistently, the nutritional value of seaweed, which has a high concentration of protein, lipids, vitamins, and fatty acids, could further contribute to the enhancement of human life and the growth of a balanced diet. Additionally, seaweed would be a more sustainable product given the rising need for plant-based nutrients, and industrial development is anticipated to be financially feasible. In this context, more research and development are needed to scale up seaweed cultivation and processing operations while taking into account factors such as acceptance by consumers, safety, and compliance with food regulations such as innovative foods or protein sources.

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The author declares that this study complies with research and publication ethics.

Informed consent

Not available.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interests for publishing of this study.

Data availability statement

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Author contribution

Md. Rahamat Ullah: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Software, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing original draft. Mousumi Akhter: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation. Abu Bakker Siddique Khan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation. Md. Monjurul Hasan: Methodology, Supervision, Writing -review & editing. Aovijite Bosu: Visualization, Supervision, Validation. Farhana Yasmin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation. Mohammed Ashraful Haque: Project administration, Supervision, Funding acquisition. Md. Amirul Islam: Project administration, Supervision, Validation. Yahia Mahmud: Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing.

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